

Computation on Corrosion Influence in Ultimate Strength and Strain Depending on Time

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Abstract— There are enough corroded steel structures, which is used in urban areas. As a result of the impact, these structural elements have begun to corrode and their operational suitability has to be checked. Corrosion impact studies on mechanical properties are sufficient in number, but there is still no definitive formula for calculating Ultimate strength and Strain. Ways should be sought to create a single equation that can be evaluated as quickly as possible with practical accuracy, as a result of corrosion, which real values are to be expected. This helps in the preliminary analysis to determine the degree of operational suitability of the steel load-bearing capacity, respectively to plan the necessary repairs and possibly to foresee at what point in time the structure will fall into an emergency state due to the corrosion effect. The negative influence of the corrosion on the steel elements has been found, mainly consisting of a reduction of the geometrical characteristics, superficial defects, a change in the structure of the material, including a change in the stress-strain diagram, i.e. the ductile material steel becomes a brittle material. I made a study and collected experimental data from corrosion influence on S355JR construction steel. I processed the results using the stochastic method and the average method. From the values obtained, I plotted the chart. I applied the polynomial approximation of establish graphs and found dependence on nonlinear equation. The equation I came to can be taken as a general equation, but the coefficients should be different depending on the corrosion resistance of steel.

Index Term— ultimate strength, ultimate strain, computation, corrosion, influence, time.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many researchers work on the influence of corrosion on mechanical properties [17-34]. There have been various experiments in this area. The key among them is that one seeks to determine at a future moment what strengths to be expected and potentially to be calculated by experimentally established formulas [17, 36]. By its very nature, corrosion has a negative impact on steel elements [18]. It is a process in which steel is destroyed as a result of aggressive factors [4]. Corrosion alters surface properties and structure of the surface layer, and also reduces the area of the supporting sections [18, 21, 35]. As a result, it directly affects the strength-deformation properties. Depending on the aggressiveness of the medium, corrosion can

occur at different speeds, respectively, its effect on mechanical

properties may be manifested in specific ways in function of time [36]. The exploitation of buildings and facilities is under constant environmental, chemical, physical, biological, and other environmental impacts. In the process, steel begins to lose its properties until it is completely destroyed [37-38]. The main factors that affect corrosion are: air, gases, water, acids, bases, temperature, solar radiation [1-8]. Steels come into contact with certain substances from the air or water, undergo a chemical change that reduces the integrity of the steel. Oxygen, sulfur, salt and other materials increase the rate of corrosion [1-8]. When the qualities of steel deteriorate, it can not bear the necessary impact as before corrosion. Structural steel used in bridges, railways and buildings (fig.1) is corroded and it is necessary to monitor and control corrosion to avoid an emergency. The classification of the corrosion category is laid down in ISO 9223, related to corrosion due to environmental impact [1-8, 35]. Classification is appropriate for structural steels, how the environment impacts them on corrosion, and is classified on a basis of 1-year loss depending on the environment in which the structural element is located. Atmospheric corrosion is the most common type of corrosion resulting from the co-action of moisture, temperature, solar radiation and environmental factors, forming a layer on the surface of the metals, which corrode [6-8]. An important factor for steel structures operating in the open - bridges, buildings, power lines, pipelines, etc. The problem is significant for steel load-bearing structural elements, as steel easily corrodes due to environmental impacts [4, 6, 8, 25, 32, 35]. Thus, the mechanical properties of steel structural elements decrease over time. Although atmospheric corrosion in steel structures is a slow process [4, 7], the impact of corrosion on ultimate strength and strain dependent time is a current problem [36]. This would establish whether there is a possibility of continued use of the corroded structure, whether repairs are necessary and whether the structure has failed in an emergency condition due to corrosion.

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Fig. 1. Urban steel structure with corrosion

II. METHODS

A. Deterministic model

In mathematics, computer science and physics, the deterministic model is a system in which no chance is involved in the development of future system states [14-15]. Therefore, the deterministic model will always produce the same result from an initial state or initial state [15]. A deterministic system can be described with differential equations of physical laws, although this system in one moment in future time, these equations are not relevant. In mathematics, the systems that study the theory of chaos are deterministic [15]. If the initial state is known, then the future state of such a system can theoretically be predicted [14]. In practice, however, the knowledge of the future state is limited by the accuracy with which the initial state can be measured, and the chaotic systems are characterized by a strong dependence on the initial conditions. In computer science and technology, the deterministic model of calculation actually represents the successive machine states and the operations to be performed are fully defined by the previous state [14]. The algorithm of the deterministic process determines that, with given input parameters, the same result will always be available and the algorithm will be calculated in the same sequence [14]. It is possible to apply non-deterministic algorithms that work on a deterministic machine, such as: an algorithm that relies on randomly selected numbers. Generally, for such random choices, a pseudo-random number generator is used, but some external physical process is used, such as the last time clock given by the computer clock [14]. The pseudo-random number generator is a deterministic algorithm that is designed to produce sequences of numbers that behave as random sequences [14-15].

This type of model can not be applied as reliable because corrosion indicates an impact depending on the random development of unrelated quantities.

B. Stochastic model

In probability theory, a stochastic process (random process) is the opposite of a deterministic process. In this method, the associated stochastic (random) areas is a process in a mathematical object, which is usually defined as a set of random variables [11-14, 16, 36]. Historically, random variables are linked or indexed by a set of numbers that are commonly regarded as time points, giving an interpretation of a stochastic process that represents numerical values of a

system that changes over time [11-14, 36]. Stochastic processes are widely used as mathematical models of systems and phenomena that seem random. They have applications in many disciplines, including sciences such as biology, chemistry, ecology, neurology, and physics, as well as engineering and engineering fields such as image processing, signal processing, information theory, computer science, cryptography and others [11-14, 36]. The term random function is also used to denote a stochastic or random process because a stochastic process can be interpreted as a random element in a functional space. The terms stochastic process and random process are used interchangeably, often without specific mathematical space for the set, which indexes random variables [11-13, 36]. But often, these two terms are used when random variables are indexed by integers or by a line from the real line. If random variables are indexed from the Cartesian plane or some higher-eyed space, then the collection of random variables is usually called a random field [11-13, 16, 36]. Stochastic process values are not always numbers and can be vectors or other mathematical objects. Based on their mathematical properties, stochastic processes can be divided into different categories, including random walks, Markov processes, Levi processes, Gaussian processes, random fields, refresh processes and branching processes [11-13, 16, 36]. The Stochastic Process Study uses mathematical knowledge and techniques of probability, calculus, linear algebra, set theory and topology, as well as branches of mathematical analysis such as real analysis, theory of measures, Fourier analysis, and functional analysis [11-13, 16, 36]. The Stochastic Process Theory is considered to be an important contribution to mathematics and remains an active subject for research both on theoretical grounds and on applications. Instead of working with one possible realization of the process over time (as in the case of solutions of a simple differential equation), there is an uncertainty in its stochastic (random process) for its future development (evolution) described by probability distributions [11-14, 36]. This means that even if the initial condition (or starting point) is known, there are many possibilities for how the process can evolve, with some conversions being more likely than others [11-13, 36].

For corroded steel, the study of certain parameters implies that they are independent random variables [16], which implies that the data processing model should be the stochastic method.

C. Polynomial approximation

In mathematics, the approximation theory deals with how best to approximate functions with simpler functions and quantify their mistakes [9-10, 17, 36]. Recognizing that what is best and simpler will depend on the application [9, 36]. Closely related is the topic of function approximation through generalized Fourier series, i.e. approximations based on the summation of a series of terms based on orthogonal polynomials [9-10, 36]. One of the problems of particular interest is the approximation of a function using operations in order for the approximation to be as close as possible to the actual function, usually with an accuracy close to that of the floating-point arithmetic of the basic parameter [9-10, 36]. This

is achieved by using a high degree and / or narrowing polynomial over which the polynomial must approach the function [9-10, 36]. Polynomials are functions with useful properties [9-10, 36]. Their relatively simple form makes them ideal for use as approximations for more complex functions [9, 36]. The polynomial in $f(x)$ is a function of the form [9, 36] (eq. 1):

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1 \cdot x + a_2 \cdot x^2 + \dots + a_n \cdot x^n \quad (1)$$

If we look at cases in which, instead of knowing function expression, we have point values [9, 36]. It is enough to find a polynomial that passes through these points, and we want the polynomial to pass through the given data, i.e. interpolating polynomial [10, 36]. Let us assume that we know (or choose to try) the function $f(x)$ exactly at several points and that we want to approximate the behavior of the function between these points [9, 36]. In its simplest form, this is equivalent to linear assembly (Fig. 2 (a)), but it is often more accurate to look for a curve that has no "angles" in it (Fig. 2 (b)) [9, 36].

Fig. 2. (a) Linear connection of the dot-to-dot principle [9, 36]; (b) dot-to-dot connection by function (no "angles") [9, 36]

In case we have experimental data after an experiment and after making a line (function), passing as close as possible to the data that is obtained [9-10, 36].

III. ESTABLISHING DEPENDENCIES

There are many studies with experimental data presented, the change of certain indicators from mechanical properties due to the corrosive impact [17-36]. These data are processed in the stochastic way and average method and the results are made a graphics. Using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], I found the equation of change the value on yield strain is determined in dependence on the time of corrosion. For each corrosion category. After I processed experimental data with stochastic way [11-14, 16-17, 36] and average method, I make up a graphics on dependence on ultimate strength and strain in time of corrosion influence i.e. $\varepsilon_u(t)$ and $\sigma_u(t)$, where t is a time in months on corrosion impact according a corrosion category.

A. Corrosion category CI

On Table I is present a result after processing by stochastic method and average method. On Fig. 3 shows the dependence between the change of the ultimate strength and strain in the time of influence of the corrosion for this category using the results indicated in Table I.

TABLE I
RESULTS AFTER PROCESSING

time, [months]	Ultimate Strain, [%]		Ultimate Strength, [MPa]	
	stochastic method	average method	stochastic method	average method
0	1.902547	1.973208	460.9131	447.1990
9138	1.891560	1.560479	448.9130	437.1476
14769	1.586107	1.562981	450.9131	441.2670
24923	1.315413	1.296142	474.7970	444.2309
34892	1.018000	0.831551	444.0000	423.6726
46154	0.874667	0.816752	446.9057	431.4203
54000	0.750220	0.800116	449.9218	442.9683
64615	0.539527	0.592498	413.9127	390.6025
73108	0.404367	0.303403	433.9137	354.4132
77262	0.228513	0.236889	451.9127	420.9715

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Graphics on dependence; (a) ultimate strain; (b) ultimate strength.

From Fig. 3, using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], a functional dependence for the change of ultimate strength and strain in the time of impact of the corrosion for this category (in months) is established depending on the chosen method of data processing (eq. 2, eq. 3, eq. 4 and eq. 5).

- Stochastic results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 4.3003913606 \cdot 10^{-41} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 1.65019893 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot t^8 + 2.667269419 \cdot 10^{-30} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 2.359985201 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^6 + 1.243303922 \cdot 10^{-20} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 3.972351371 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^4 + 7.491859784 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 7.637135628 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot t^2 + 3.010721725 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t + \\ & 1.902706585 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 4.567188873 \cdot 10^{-39} \cdot t^9 - 1.23691171 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^8 + \\ & 3.422275948 \cdot 10^{-28} \cdot t^7 - 3.232953691 \cdot 10^{-23} \cdot t^6 + \\ & 1.775685996 \cdot 10^{-18} \cdot t^5 - 5.726521554 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^4 + \\ & 1.037518148 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^3 - 9.371899552 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^2 + \\ & 3.08709247 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t + 461.1038654 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

• Average results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 6.161570328 \cdot 10^{-41} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 2.239821925 \cdot 10^{-35} \cdot t^8 + 3.399410323 \cdot 10^{-30} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 2.779694866 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^6 + 1.315871686 \cdot 10^{-20} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 3.594117404 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^4 + 5.29231186 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 3.521603834 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot t^2 + 3.30542855 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t + \\ & 1.973359434 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 2.525880003 \cdot 10^{-40} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 1.839988163 \cdot 10^{-34} \cdot t^8 + 4.541831589 \cdot 10^{-29} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 5.368275473 \cdot 10^{-24} \cdot t^6 + 3.399263928 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 1.178006275 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^4 + 2.131693936 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 1.745600812 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^2 + 3.980608075 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t + \\ & 447.3706767 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

B. Corrosion category C2

TABLE II
RESULTS AFTER PROCESSING

time, [months]	Ultimate Strain, [%]		Ultimate Strength, [MPa]	
	stochastic method	average method	stochastic method	average method
0	1.902547	1.973208	460.9131	447.1990
475	1.891560	1.560479	448.9130	437.1476
768	1.586107	1.562981	450.9131	441.2670
1296	1.315413	1.296142	474.7970	444.2309
1814	1.018000	0.831551	444.0000	423.6726
2400	0.874667	0.816752	446.9057	431.4203
2808	0.750220	0.800116	449.9218	442.9683
3360	0.539527	0.592498	413.9127	390.6025
3802	0.404367	0.303403	433.9137	354.4132
4018	0.228513	0.236889	451.9127	420.9715

On Table II is present a result after processing by stochastic method and average method. On Fig. 4 shows the dependence between the change of the ultimate strength and strain in the

time of influence of the corrosion for this category using the results indicated in Table II.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Graphics on dependence; (a) ultimate strain; (b) ultimate strength.

From Fig. 4, using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], a functional dependence for the change of ultimate strength and strain in the time of impact of the corrosion for this category (in months) is established depending on the chosen method of data processing (eq. 6, eq. 7, eq. 8 and eq. 9).

• Stochastic results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 1.548441942 \cdot 10^{-29} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 3.089574242 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^8 + 2.596598942 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.19460109 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot t^6 + 3.272397952 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 5.436387356 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^4 + 5.33118141 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 2.825724466 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^2 + 5.792219254 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t + \\ & 1.902528851 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 1.645364274 \cdot 10^{-27} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 3.641210131 \cdot 10^{-23} \cdot t^8 + 3.332389085 \cdot 10^{-19} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.636749255 \cdot 10^{-15} \cdot t^6 + 4.674167537 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 7.837825826 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^4 + 7.383770237 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 3.468278766 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t^2 + 5.943745247 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t + \\ & 460.9000627 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

• Average results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 2.218270013 \cdot 10^{-29} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 4.193093337 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^8 + 3.309209528 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.407086855 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot t^6 + 3.463755929 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 4.919823399 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^4 + 3.767515111 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 1.304002088 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^2 + 6.38555307 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t + \\ & 1.973191712 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 9.122548483 \cdot 10^{-29} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 3.448603062 \cdot 10^{-24} \cdot t^8 + 4.423123542 \cdot 10^{-20} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 2.717538314 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^6 + 8.946267509 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 1.611970765 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^4 + 1.516739114 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 6.459404718 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^2 + 7.687300964 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t + \\ & 447.1870387 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

C. Corrosion category C3

On Table III is present a result after processing by stochastic method and average method. On Fig. 5 shows the dependence between the change of the ultimate strength and strain in the time of influence of the corrosion for this category using the results indicated in Table III.

TABLE III
RESULTS AFTER PROCESSING

time, [months]	Ultimate Strain, [%]		Ultimate Strength, [MPa]	
	stochastic method	average method	stochastic method	average method
0	1.902547	1.973208	460.9131	447.1990
238	1.891560	1.560479	448.9130	437.1476
384	1.586107	1.562981	450.9131	441.2670
648	1.315413	1.296142	474.7970	444.2309
907	1.018000	0.831551	444.0000	423.6726
1200	0.874667	0.816752	446.9057	431.4203
1404	0.750220	0.800116	449.9218	442.9683
1680	0.539527	0.592498	413.9127	390.6025
1901	0.404367	0.303403	433.9137	354.4132
2009	0.228513	0.236889	451.9127	420.9715

(b) Fig. 5. Graphics on dependence; (a) ultimate strain; (b) ultimate strength.

From Fig. 5, using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], a functional dependence for the change of ultimate strength and strain in the time of impact of the corrosion for this category (in months) is established depending on the chosen method of data processing (eq. 10, eq. 11, eq. 12 and eq. 13).

- Stochastic results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 7.928022742 \cdot 10^{-27} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 7.909310059 \cdot 10^{-23} \cdot t^8 + 3.323646646 \cdot 10^{-19} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 7.645446979 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^6 + 1.047167345 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 8.69821977 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^4 + 4.264945128 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 1.130289786 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^2 + 1.158443851 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t + \\ & 1.902528851 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 8.412784552 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 9.310787721 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^8 + 4.261266584 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.046626366 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot t^6 + 1.494609337 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 1.253204301 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^4 + 5.903288809 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 1.386401322 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t^2 + 1.187672313 \cdot t + 460.8595 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

- Average results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 1.135754247 \cdot 10^{-26} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 1.073431894 \cdot 10^{-22} \cdot t^8 + 4.235788196 \cdot 10^{-19} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 9.005355869 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^6 + 1.108401897 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 7.871717438 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^4 + 3.014012089 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 5.216008353 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^2 + 1.277110614 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t + \\ & 1.973191712 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 4.668501948 \cdot 10^{-26} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 8.826285475 \cdot 10^{-22} \cdot t^8 + 5.660739384 \cdot 10^{-18} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.73903498 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^6 + 2.862555787 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 2.578950387 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot t^4 + 1.213259191 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 0.002582563 \cdot t^2 + 0.153086761 \cdot t + 447.1776509 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

(a)

D. Corrosion category C4

On Table IV is present a result after processing by stochastic method and average method. On Fig. 6 shows the dependence between the change of the ultimate strength and

strain in the time of influence of the corrosion for this category using the results indicated in Table IV.

TABLE IV
RESULTS AFTER PROCESSING

time, [months]	Ultimate Strain, [%]		Ultimate Strength, [MPa]	
	stochastic method	average method	stochastic method	average method
0	1.902547	1.973208	460.9131	447.1990
149	1.891560	1.560479	448.9130	437.1476
240	1.586107	1.562981	450.9131	441.2670
405	1.315413	1.296142	474.7970	444.2309
567	1.018000	0.831551	444.0000	423.6726
750	0.874667	0.816752	446.9057	431.4203
878	0.750220	0.800116	449.9218	442.9683
1050	0.539527	0.592498	413.9127	390.6025
1188	0.404367	0.303403	433.9137	354.4132
1256	0.228513	0.236889	451.9127	420.9715

Fig. 6. Graphics on dependence; (a) ultimate strain; (b) ultimate strength.

From Fig. 6, using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], a functional dependence for the change of ultimate strength and strain in the time of impact of the corrosion for this category (in months) is established depending on the chosen method of data processing (eq. 14, eq. 15, eq. 16 and eq. 17).

- Stochastic results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 5.45086278 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 13.398641753 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^8 + 8.925821873 \cdot 10^{-18} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.283225109 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^6 + 1.098455418 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 5.702462184 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^4 + 1.747469893 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 2.894336336 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^2 + 1.854029757 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t + \\ & 1.902466422 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 5.779625236 \cdot 10^{-23} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 3.998021118 \cdot 10^{-19} \cdot t^8 + 1.143646822 \cdot 10^{-15} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.755643381 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^6 + 1.566971716 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 8.211864007 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^4 + 2.41766385 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 3.548515087 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t^2 + 1.898626957 \cdot t + 461.0399 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

- Average results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 7.808116126 \cdot 10^{-25} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 4.612269795 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^8 + 1.137506092 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 1.511477448 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^6 + 1.162741735 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 5.161172686 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^4 + 1.235188752 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 1.336237386 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^2 + 2.049356457 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t + \\ & 1.973132437 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 3.197066486 \cdot 10^{-24} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 3.784406071 \cdot 10^{-20} \cdot t^8 + 1.517969995 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 2.915533043 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot t^6 + 2.999983352 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 1.689384934 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^4 + 4.967411633 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 6.607358751 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t^2 + 2.440773845 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t + \\ & 447.3132612 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

E. Corrosion category C5

On Table V is present a result after processing by stochastic method and average method. On Fig. 7 shows the dependence between the change of the ultimate strength and strain in the time of influence of the corrosion for this category using the results indicated in Table V.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Graphics on dependence; (a) ultimate strain; (b) ultimate strength.

TABLE V
RESULTS AFTER PROCESSING

time, [months]	Ultimate Strain, [%]		Ultimate Strength, [MPa]	
	stochastic method	average method	stochastic method	average method
0	1.902547	1.973208	460.9131	447.1990
59	1.891560	1.560479	448.9130	437.1476
96	1.586107	1.562981	450.9131	441.2670
162	1.315413	1.296142	474.7970	444.2309
227	1.018000	0.831551	444.0000	423.6726
300	0.874667	0.816752	446.9057	431.4203
351	0.750220	0.800116	449.9218	442.9683
420	0.539527	0.592498	413.9127	390.6025
475	0.404367	0.303403	433.9137	354.4132
502	0.228513	0.236889	451.9127	420.9715

From Fig. 7, using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], a functional dependence for the change of ultimate strength and strain in the time of impact of the corrosion for this category (in months) is established depending on the chosen method of data processing (eq. 18, eq. 19, eq. 20 and eq. 21).

- Stochastic results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 2.078283594 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^9 - 5.18344544 \cdot 10^{-18} \cdot t^8 + \\ & 5.445462665 \cdot 10^{-15} \cdot t^7 - 3.131575082 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^6 + \\ & 1.072299361 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^5 - 2.226744261 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^4 + \\ & 2.729564882 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^3 - 1.808463658 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t^2 + \\ & 4.633775403 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t + 1.902528851 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 2.204714117 \cdot 10^{-19} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 6.100408791 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^8 + 6.980182659 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 4.286195238 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^6 + 1.530232374 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 3.207733895 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^4 + 3.777577986 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 2.217892484 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t^2 + 4.749452975 \cdot t + 460.8248 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

- Average results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 2.974636691 \cdot 10^{-21} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 7.028621433 \cdot 10^{-18} \cdot t^8 + 6.933846836 \cdot 10^{-15} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 3.685372869 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^6 + 1.133994113 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 2.013265093 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^4 + 1.926911876 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 8.333989589 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^2 + 5.083255354 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t + \\ & 1.973141129 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 1.223819775 \cdot 10^{-20} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 5.784394449 \cdot 10^{-17} \cdot t^8 + 9.274555408 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 7.123087276 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^6 + 2.931257126 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 6.60211299 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t^4 + 7.764858819 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 0.041321008 \cdot t^2 + 6.123470441 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t + 447.1776 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

F. Corrosion category CX

On Table VI is present a result after processing by stochastic method and average method.

TABLE VI
RESULTS AFTER PROCESSING

time, [months]	Ultimate Strain, [%]		Ultimate Strength, [MPa]	
	stochastic method	average method	stochastic method	average method
0	1.902547	1.973208	460.9131	447.1990
17	1.891560	1.560479	448.9130	437.1476
27	1.586107	1.562981	450.9131	441.2670
46	1.315413	1.296142	474.7970	444.2309
65	1.018000	0.831551	444.0000	423.6726
86	0.874667	0.816752	446.9057	431.4203
100	0.750220	0.800116	449.9218	442.9683
120	0.539527	0.592498	413.9127	390.6025
136	0.404367	0.303403	433.9137	354.4132
143	0.228513	0.236889	451.9127	420.9715

On Fig. 8 shows the dependence between the change of the ultimate strength and strain in the time of influence of the corrosion for this category using the results indicated in Table VI.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Graphics on dependence: (a) ultimate strain; (b) ultimate strength.

From Fig. 8, using the polynomial approximation [9-10, 17, 36], a functional dependence for the change of ultimate strength and strain in the time of impact of the corrosion for this category (in months) is established depending on the chosen method of data processing (eq. 22, eq. 23, eq. 24 and eq. 25).

- Stochastic results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 1.636582059 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 1.166294349 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot t^8 + 3.50090905 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 5.752614746 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^6 + 5.628275319 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 3.339546908 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^4 + 1.169690779 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 2.214387894 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t^2 + 1.621240644 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t + \\ & 1.902536082 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 1.738115986 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 1.374036524 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^8 + 4.491828381 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 7.880405146 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^6 + 8.038163082 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 4.814188134 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot t^4 + 1.619825107 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 2.7173393 \cdot t^2 + 16.62781185 \cdot t + 460.8995351 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

- Average results:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_u(t) = & 2.344858317 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^9 - \\ & 1.583007264 \cdot 10^{-13} \cdot t^8 + 4.461873874 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot t^7 - \\ & 6.775717808 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^6 + 5.956849655 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^5 - \\ & 3.0216285 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^4 + 8.263072059 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^3 - \\ & 1.02114967 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t^2 + 1.780792068 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t + \\ & 1.973198448 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_u(t) = & 9.612900156 \cdot 10^{-16} \cdot t^9 - 1.30039439 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot t^8 + \\ & 5.961097449 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot t^7 - 1.308489086 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot t^6 + \\ & 1.538727554 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t^5 - 9.902929742 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot t^4 + \\ & 3.327917168 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot t^3 - 5.060988776 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot t^2 + \\ & 2.147562057 \cdot t + 447.1868122 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Probability of results – stochastic results is 81.32 % and average results is 75.85 %.

If I remove values from the formulas, I establish with sufficient practical accuracy, a basic non-linear equation [17, 36]

(eq. 26 and eq. 27):

$$\varepsilon_u(t) = A_1 \cdot t^9 + A_2 \cdot t^8 + A_3 \cdot t^7 + A_4 \cdot t^6 + A_5 \cdot t^5 + A_6 \cdot t^4 + A_7 \cdot t^3 + A_8 \cdot t^2 + A_9 \cdot t + \varepsilon_u \quad (26)$$

Where: $A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5, A_6, A_7, A_8$ and A_9 is constant values and need to be determined experimentally in every case [36].

$$\sigma_u(t) = B_1 \cdot t^9 + B_2 \cdot t^8 + B_3 \cdot t^7 + B_4 \cdot t^6 + B_5 \cdot t^5 + B_6 \cdot t^4 + B_7 \cdot t^3 + B_8 \cdot t^2 + B_9 \cdot t + \sigma_u \quad (27)$$

Where: $B_1, B_2, B_3, B_4, B_5, B_6, B_7, B_8$ and B_9 is constant values and need to be determined experimentally in every case.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper found that the change of ultimate strength and strain depending on time of corrosion influence is not a linear function of the 9th degree with different coefficients. These factors depend on the type of steel, the chemical composition, the corrosion resistance and other specific characteristics of the steel concerned.

It was found that the dependence of a change on ultimate strength and strain is a one-time function that has been stretched over time, due to the fact that, according to the standard, the different corrosion categories are determined depending on the loss of section (weight loss) for 1 year i.e. the higher the corroded category, the faster the values of ultimate strength and strain for a shorter time. There can be no doubt that there is a correlation between the rate of corrosion and the change in the mechanical properties of steel. Established dependence formulas can be applied in practice to quickly assess the condition of the corroded steel element and can be used to predict changes in these values over time ultimate strength and strain. This makes it possible to predict the possible occurrence of an emergency state of the steel structural element as a consequence of the corrosion effect or to determine its residual reliability with sufficient practical justification.

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